

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE MARINE PROPELLER FOR A FISHING BOAT BY FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

For developing more effective and affordable propellers, application of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) has great potential. In order to design CFRP propeller with consideration of its elastic property, fluid structure interaction analysis (FSIA) is essential. We implemented an FSIA for propeller design by applying lifting surface theory (LST) and finite element analysis (FEA). For validating this analysis system with a tank test, scaled down propeller, which fits the tank was developed by using a similarity rule about elasticity. After that computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and FEA were coupled for FSIA to be able to consider real fluid, hull/ladder.

1 Introduction

Ship propeller is usually made of stiff metal material as nickel aluminum bronze (NAB). For such metal propellers, various researches, including optimization of blade configuration and recovery loss of flow energy with contra-rotating propeller, have already been performed to increase propeller efficiency. Now the design method around metal propeller is so optimized. On the other hand, Bronze and some other materials for propellers are exhaustible resources, thus their market prices may stay high or even become higher in near future. In the light of these situations, demand for alternative material for propeller is increasing.

In order to develop more effective and affordable propellers, we are researching the possibility of applying FRP to marine propeller, in particular, CFRP. In the marine fields, CFRP materials have

already been used to the hulls of boats and yachts excluding huge vessels [1]. Recently, the studies of marine propellers are also focused on the application of composite materials. CFRP contributes to propeller's durability with its good fatigue property and high specific strength/stiffness. In addition, total performance of the propeller (e.g. efficiency, accelerating performance) will be improved compared to stiff metal propeller, leading desirable elastic deformation caused by elastic property of CFRP [2]. In terms of material cost, expanding usages in various fields and progress of production technologies for composite materials will reduce the cost. Consequently, we can say that the composite materials have great potential for marine propellers in terms of efficiency and cost.

For investigating the feasibility of CFRP propeller, we have evaluated its properties from various aspects; cavitation erosion resistance, mechanical property, vibration characteristic and general performance, by universal testing methods and field test with a fishing boat [3]. In particular, the difference of elastic property between metal materials and CFRP is needed to be careful in modeling for numerical analysis. In the case of metal material, the propeller is regarded as a rigid structure, thus the thrust performance can be estimated only by fluid analysis with LST or CFD. In the case of CFRP propeller, however, the performance cannot be evaluated precisely only by fluid analysis. Because elastic coefficient of CFRP is generally lower than NAB, the shape of CFRP propeller can be deformed from its initial shape by fluid force. Accordingly this deformation causes variation of general performance of the propeller. Thus, in order to evaluate the performance accurately, not only fluid analysis, but

also coupling between structural and fluid conditions is needed. This simultaneous calculation with fluid and structural analysis, known as FSIA is studied extensively in many fields [3]. As for the marine field, however, reliable method has not been established [4].

Some ways to implement fluid analysis of FSIA have been researched in the marine field. Here three examples are introduced; LST, boundary element method (BEM) and CFD. In the field of propeller design, LST has been used majorly to design metal propellers and shown enough precision to design, thus LST is expected to work well also in FSIA. As for BEM, some design methodologies to optimize the performance of self-twisting composite propellers were implemented with FEA and BEM [4,5]. When CFD is used, it does not need to be modified depend on the scale, thus same CFD model can be applied from a scaled-down propeller to an actual propeller. In addition, CFD can consider the interference with hull or rudder which is difficult to observe by experiment or consider directly in LST. Furthermore, CFD can estimate elastic deformation from high load condition to low load condition, therefore it is compatible with CFRP propeller, which changes its shape during acceleration.

The goal of our study has been set to establish designing method for optimizing CFRP propeller shape by FSIA. Therefore, in order to build a numerical system which can consider elastic deformations during rotation, we combined LST and FEA and validated the system with a tank test. After that we have substituted CFD for LST to utilize advantages above. The present paper is organized as follows. In the next session, the configuration of the CFRP propeller is outlined. After that, an FSIA calculation system is established with LST-FEA and this is validated with tank test. Lastly, a CFD-FEA calculation system is established to achieve more compatible simulation for CFRP propeller.

2 Design of CFRP propeller

2.2 Configuration of the fishing boat

Present propellers were designed assuming the usage on the small fishing boat as follows. We have a plan to implement field tests using an actual ship test after the tank test.

Gross tonnage	: 3.3G/T
Loa × B × D	: 10.50 m × 2.75 m × 1.4 m
Output power	: 221 kW / 2600 min ⁻¹ (i=2.58)
Propeller speed	: 1008 min ⁻¹
Ship speed	: approx. 26 knots (13.4 m/s)

2.2 Design of Propeller

The shape of CFRP propeller was designed based on existing metallic propeller of the ship above. Specification of the propeller is as follows.

Number of blade Z	: 3
Propeller diameter D	: 680 mm
Propeller pitch H	: 1120mm($H/D=1.647$)
Boss diameter B	: 136 mm($B/D=0.20$)
Expanded propeller area ratio A_e	: 0.55

This CFRP propeller is a built-up type of 3-blades and 1- boss. The structural concept is shown in Fig.2. The blades and the boss are made of CFRP and NAB, respectively, and the boss has grooves for installing the blades. The blades are inserted into the grooves from the boss's rear, and they are fixed with the retaining ring of the omission stop. Properties of CFRP for the present propeller are shown in Table.1. Basic mechanical properties of these materials are investigated and confirmed to be safe in use for marine propellers [3].

Although the actual propeller's diameter is 680 mm, we designed scaled-down propeller models with diameters of 250 mm were designed. This is for fitting them in cavitation tank. It enables us to compare the results of LST or CFD with those of the tank test. In the case that scaled down models are used, displacement ratio (displacement / diameter of propeller) is smaller than that of actual propeller. Thus, in order to match those displacement rates and observe the effect of displacement, polyvinyl chloride was chosen for material, according to the following similarity rule.

$$\delta \propto \frac{L \cdot l^3}{E \cdot I} \propto \frac{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^3}{E} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{D} \propto \frac{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^2}{E} \quad (2)$$

where δ is the displacement, L the lift force, l the point of action, E the elastic modulus, I the second moment of area, ρ the density of fluid, n the number of rotations, D the diameter of propeller. The bending elastic modulus of model propeller E_m is derived from following equation (3).

$$E_m = \frac{\rho_m \cdot n_m^2 \cdot D_m^2}{\rho_a \cdot n_a^2 \cdot D_a^2} E_a \quad (3)$$

where E_a is the bending elastic modulus of actual propeller, D_a the diameter of actual propeller, D_m the diameter of model propeller, n_a the diameter of propeller, n_m the number of rotations of model propeller, ρ_a the density of sea water ρ_m the density of water in cavitaion tank.

Consequently three kinds of model propellers are designed, considering input power, number of rotation, ship speed, wake coefficient, hull dimensions. Configurations of these propellers are shown in Table.2.

3 Predeformed design with LST-FEM

3.1 Procedure of the design

Based on these blades, optimal initial shapes are designed applying the concept of predeformed design. This concept is that a blade is installed in an opposite direction to its deformation, so that it returns to the optimal shape with designed torque, thrust and efficiency values [6]. We implemented this concept with LST-FEA. Specific procedure is following. For FEA, I-DEAS 12NXm was used.

1. Obtain the pressure distribution on the blade surface of the propeller model by LST
2. Calculate stress and displacement by FEA
3. Deduct the difference between the deformed shape and the optimal shape from the original

shape, in order to estimate the optimal initial shape.

4. Apply FEA for the initial shape generated in 3., with stress distribution of optimized blade shape

This procedure is continued until the difference of deformed shape and optimal shape is ignorable. At the same time, this designing system with LFD-FEA was verified by comparing calculated displacement and general performance with those of the tank test. Our tank test was carried out in a cavitations tank (Fig. 3.). The displacement was measured by utilizing a verified method, tracing laser beam at certain points on the blade. Thrust coefficient (KT), torque efficient (KQ) and other performance indicators were measured by a dynamometer.

3.2 Comparison with the tank test

To measure the accuracy of LST-FEA for evaluating performance of propellers, indicators of propeller efficiency; KT, KQ and open propeller efficiency (η_o) were compared with those of the tank test. The displacements of the leading edge and trading edge at radial positions are also observed as for three different propellers in the Table 2. Five kinds of conditions ($J = 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.136$) were applied for each propeller. Each indicator is defined as follows.

$$KT = \frac{T}{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^4} \quad (4)$$

$$KQ = \frac{T}{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^5} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_o = \frac{J}{2n} \frac{KT}{KQ} \quad (6)$$

$$J = \frac{V}{nD} \quad (7)$$

Where ρ is the fluid density, n the rotation number, D the diameter of propeller, T the thrust output, Q the torque output, J the advance coefficient, V the axial velocity.

The results are shown in the Figs. 4 and 5. Fig. 4 illustrates indicators of propeller efficiency of the three models. Triangle plots express the ratio of LST to tank test. If this is lower than 1, it means that LST underestimate performances. The errors of thrust, torque and efficiency are less than 5% excluding No. 1-5. The error can be caused by modeling for LST. That's because a rigid metal blade which has same shape as No.1-5 have shown similar trend as No.1-5. It implies that this error doesn't come from displacement of blade, thus it can be said that this error can be occurred in fluid calculation.

Fig. 5 illustrates the axial displacement of propeller No 1-7 in LST-FEA and the tank test. At design point $J = 1.136$, they show good consistency with errors less than 0.3mm. In addition the trend of errors, which underestimate displacement, is consistent with those of indicators of performance. However, the displacement errors tend to increase apart from the design point as the plots at $J = 0.8$, 0.4 express. This is because LST can only consider ideal fluid and the accuracy is not guaranteed when J is low.

4 Performance evaluation with CFD-FEM

In accord with the results of LST-FEA, CFD-FEA may have benefits including three points below. Firstly, CFD can consider real fluid and keep accurate even when J is low. Secondly, CFD can also consider the interference with hull or rudder, which is difficult to observe by experiment or consider directly in LST. Lastly, CFD's mesh and boundary conditions don't need to be modified depend on the scale, thus same CFD model can be applied from a scaled-down propeller to an actual propeller. We have developed a CFD-FEA system and validated it with tank test by comparing performance indicators and axial displacements. This system was implemented with ANSYS FLUENT for CFD, ANSYS FEA. The mesh for ANSYS is shown in Fig.6. In the process of FSIA, first, CFD calculation is carried out for the original shape of the blade to simulate fluid force on each CFD nodes. Second, the nodal fluid forces are redistributed to FEA nodes. Third, FEA calculation is performed to simulate deformation of the blade. These processes are repeated until convergence.

After that, as the case of LST, general performances and displacements are compared with the tank test.

The results are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. Fig. 7 illustrates K_T and K_Q of Propeller No.1-7. Triangle plots express the ratio of CFD to tank test. K_T has a large margin of error. This error may occur in CFD calculation because this error is observed from the first CFD calculation along the CFD-FEA procedure. Now we are investigating this CFD calculation by applying it for other models.

Fig. 8 indicates that errors at design point $J = 1.136$ are larger than LST. Apparently these errors are mainly due to errors of K_T or K_Q . These trends are consistent. Another reason for these errors can be FEA model. When Scaling down the blade in 2.2, FEA model was simply downscaled by the ratio of model to actual blade. Thus its mounting part to the boss may not be modeled correctly.

On the other hand, the margin of errors at $J = 0.4$ is smaller than that of LST. It can be said that CFD-FEA has the potential to perform accurate performance evaluation even when J is low.

5 Conclusions

A method for optimizing CFRP propeller by FSIA was investigated. The first method applying LST-FEA was validated with tank test, by performing a sample test using scaled down propeller. This propeller was developed by using a similarity rule about elasticity for fitting it in the tank. After that, CFD was substituted for LST and this system showed the advantage that it can consider real fluid. We will investigate accuracy of CFD-FEA more precisely.

Fig.1. CFRP propeller

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Fig.2. Concept of built-up CFRP propeller

Fig.3. Tank test in cavitation tank

Fig.4. Performance results of LST-FEM and tank test ($J = 1.136$)

Fig.5. Displacement results in LSTFEM and tank test (axial displacement, propeller 1-7)

Fig.6. FEM mesh model on FSIA

Fig.7. Performance results of CFD-FEM and tank test ($J = 1.136$)

Fig.8. Displacement results in CFDFEM and tank test (axial displacement, propeller 1-7)

Table 1. Properties of CFRP

	CFRP-Fabric-iso	CFRP-UD-iso
Fiber	Carbon	Carbon
Textile	Fabric	Uni-Direction
Matrix	Epoxy	Epoxy
Orientation and standing	[$\pm 45/0, 90/\pm 45/0, 90$] ₂	[$+45/0/-45/90/90/-45/0/+45$] ₂
Property	Quasi-isotropy	Quasi-isotropy
Fabrication	Prepreg-Autoclave	Prepreg-Autoclave
Thickness (mm)	1.78 \pm 0.02	1.95 \pm 0.02
Vf (%)	51	55
Density (kg/m ³)	1,490	1,540

Table 2. Configurations of propellers

	1-5	1-6	1-7
Material	Polyvinyl chloride		
Number of blades	3		
Diameter (mm)	250		
Section	MAU	NACA	NACA
Pitch ratio 0.7r	1.647	1.737	1.675
Area ratio	0.55	0.44	0.55
Boss ratio	0.2		
Thickness/chord 0.7r	0.04375	0.04443	0.04375
Skew angle	20	35	
Rake angle	8	10.8	10.3
Rotation	Right hand		

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